

Meeting Summary

of the business meeting @ MEDINFO 2015, Aug 22, Sao Paulo
Ronald Cornet, Stefan Schulz, Laszlo Balkanyi

Why?

The business meeting was called by the leadership and the active members of the WG in order to (1) report the last period, (2) report the change in the leadership, (3) present the ideas of the new chair, and to discuss and get input from interested participants for further vitalization of the working group as a whole.

Who?

Participants were invited by expressed interest, networks of active members, mailing lists and social media (relevant LinkedIn groups), by the merits for earlier activities and by having relevant publications at MEDINFO 2015. The invitation, as earlier, was open and it was reposted to well over hundred interested parties. At the meeting 15 participants were registered (despite the early morning time slot).

What it was About?

First, the accomplishments of the past chairing period were reported:

- a new name for the Working Group: “**Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (LaMB)**”

This was initiated at the 2013 business meeting and was later endorsed by IMIA. The reasons for changing the working group name were summarized as: we need (1) to cover “representation” in a broader sense, (2) to cover differentiated subjects of representations: clinical reality, information items, word meanings should be covered, etc.

- active members published the results of [our 2013 survey and bibliometric study](#) and developed it to a publication, “[From Concept Representations to Ontologies: A Paradigm Shift in Health Informatics?](#)”,

showing the characteristics of the paradigm shift from “concept representation” to a very wide area stretching from understanding and using medical natural language towards knowledge representation, ontologies and other formal tools, including the broad world of medical terminology systems.

- the WG maintains a **LinkedIn Group**, currently with well over 90 interested members

This LinkedIn Site had over twenty postings, mostly reporting on our activities. For the latest announcements we had well over a hundred views, see here: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=3680642&trk=anet Ug hm>,

- to **share and work on content**, the WG has a WordPress site: <https://imiawg6lamb.wordpress.com/>

Originally we established a wiki site that was retired following the change of the hosting site policy (no free services anymore). The current site contains legacy contents and reports, content regarding our ongoing activities.

- recently, the WG **organized and hosted a workshop** at MEDINFO 2015, titled as “**Biomedical Semantics in the Big Data Era**”

The workshop was well attended, having presenters as follows:

- Tomasz Adamusiak (Thomson Reuters, Boston, MA, USA), AMIA KR +S WG
- Ronald Cornet (Academic Medical Center University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands & Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden) IMIA LaMB
- Jianying Hu (IBM T. J. Watson Research Center, Yorktown Heights, NY, USA), AMIA KDDM WG
- Stephane Meystre (University of Utah, Salt Lake City, Utah, USA) AMIA NLP WG
- Patrick Ruch (University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland, Geneva, Switzerland) EFMI NLP WG
- Stefan Schulz (Medical University of Graz, Graz, Austria) IMIA LaMB WG,
- concept mapped and summed up by Laszlo Balkanyi, IMIA LaMB wg.

The full presentation material is available here: https://imiawg6lamb.files.wordpress.com/2015/08/20150821_medinfo_lamb-final.pdf

Secondly, the change of leadership was announced, as approved by IMIA GA:

- *Stefan Schulz*, the outgoing chair after two periods, will further support the Working Group as Co-Chair.
- *Ronald Cornet* is the new Chair of IMIA LaMB Working Group.
- *Laszlo Balkanyi* will remain as Co-Chair, focusing on the group admin function, operating the LinkedIn site and the WordPress site.

Thirdly, the new chair, Ronald Cornet presented his views, suggestions on future works, see the presentation attached to the end of this report that was discussed with the audience with the participants of the meeting.

The new Chair emphasized, that, while keeping the continuity with the previous period, he suggest to bring closer the WG activities to meet common IMIA goals, as specified in details in the presentations. IMIA goals for the period 2016-2030 are be the following: IMIA should act as a bridging organization for

- connecting research to practice and policy: to translate eHealth research into Universal Health Coverage (UHC) practice and policy
- connecting developing countries with the developed world: to share the courtiers’ experience in UHC in the most effective way
- connecting international organizations working in health: to harmonize the frameworks developed by international organizations working in health to achieve UHC
- connecting people with health and technology: to efficiently build the required capacity for UHC

The tasks of the LaMB WG has been and will be:

- reviewing health data nomenclature and classification needs for the world community
- evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs
- recommending methods for future classification and nomenclature systems.

Keeping continuity means to deal with the overall scientific area of biomedical semantics – including the natural language domain as there is no other IMIA WG to deal with this broad territory. The WG will retain its approach not focusing on particular technologies or tools as e.g. ontologies. We keep our intent to take a look at biomedical ontology/NLP “in action”.

Summary of the discussion at the meeting, suggesting also work areas, possible deliverables

This short summary just mentions the essence of what was discussed:

- carry on idea from the workshop the day before: The WG should not be a “language police” – although we might perhaps describe inconsistent use of words for sub communities and guide gently toward some consolidation
- the WP should formally clarify its position to the IMIA strategic plan
- there is a need to bridge bioinformatics language&resources and clinical informatics language&resources, there is clearly a gap there
- the WG should contribute to e-learning and innovation in its area, e.g. by some setting some quality (accreditations?) measures,

- harmonization of research results is also a task to be considered (follow up, reviews of the field, apply some knowledge extraction techs over its own field)
- there is need for assessment frameworks
- the LaMB WG could
 - o review health data nomenclature and classification needs, evaluating information processing technologies
 - o recommend methods
 - o promote NLP in less common languages
 - o take part in painting the landscape of standards
 - o keeping an overview on application of semantic technologies

The leadership of the WG offered to analyse the suggestions and come back to the participants by using the WG workbench: the LinkedIn group, the WordPress site and possibly by other new initiatives. The list of participants will be compiled and checked against the LinkedIn group site to ensure invitation of all interested parties who are not yet in the group.

Attachment: Presentation of the new chair, Ronald Cornet

IMIA Working group 6 – Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (LaMB)

REMEMBER, THERE'S NO "I" IN "TEAM!"

NO, BUT THERE'S A "U" IN "PEOPLE WHO APPARENTLY DON'T UNDERSTAND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORTHOGRAPHY AND MEANING."

ideas for 2016-2019

Ronald Cornet

Future of IMIA (2016-2030)

- Universal Health Coverage (UHC) is an essential component
- IMIA should act as a bridging organization for
 - Connecting **research to practice and policy**: to translate eHealth research into UHC practice and policy
 - Connecting **developing countries with the developed world**: to share the courtiers' experience in UHC in the most effective way
 - Connecting **international organizations working in health**: to harmonize the frameworks developed by international organizations working in health to achieve UHC
 - Connecting **people with health and technology**: to efficiently build the required capacity for UHC

By empowering all IMIA members to participate

- in education
 - recommendations, accreditation, certification
- in research
 - Harmonizing ... research efforts in developing eHealth standardization and evaluation frameworks
 - Developing country case studies in utilizing eHealth in health systems
- in service
 - Developing the IMIA innovation portal that will provide an interactive "health innovation opportunity guide" and an eLearning platform for capacity building
- in innovation

LaMB "tasks"

1. Reviewing health data nomenclature and classification **needs for the world community**
2. **Evaluating** information processing technology in meeting these defined needs
3. **Recommending methods** for future classification and nomenclature systems

LaMB approaches

- Technical
- "Political"
- Educational

Collaboration opportunities

- Natural language processing in less common languages
- Painting the standards landscape: overlaps, omissions and opportunities
- Application of semantic (web) technologies to enhance capture, storage and retrieval of data

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History

- Established 1981
- 1997 Jacksonville
- 1999 Phoenix
- 2005 Rome

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Challenge...(?)

- An expert meeting in 2018, commemorating 90 years of “logical clinical nomenclature”

2. Arrival of medical nomenclatures

On 22 March 1928, the New York Academy of Medicine officially sponsored the National Conference on Nomenclature of Disease. The purpose was to present a logical clinical nomenclature having two axes; topography and etiology (disease).

Farr, 1839

- “The advantages of a uniform nomenclature, however imperfect, are so obvious, that it is surprising no attention has been paid to its enforcement in Bills of Mortality. ... The nomenclature is of as much importance in this department of enquiry as weights and measures in the physical sciences, and should be settled without delay”

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